

The apparent brightness of exoplanets

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Abstract: First the apparent brightness of planets are determined generally and then at inclined circular orbits. At last an example with two exoplanets is treated.

Key words: Brightness - phase - phase angle - circular orbit - planet - magnitude

1 Foundations

We want to inquire into the apparent brightness of a planet in dependence of its motion. We introduce the following quantities:

$\vec{r}_s(t)$ = position of a **self-luminous** body S (fixed star)

$\vec{r}_p(t)$ = position of a irradiated body P (planet), P is not self-luminous.

$\vec{r}_B(t)$ = position of another body B (planet) with an observer. B isn't self-luminous.

$\vec{r}_s, \vec{r}_B, \vec{r}_p \in R^3$ $t = \text{time}$

Presumption: P and B possess **no** atmospheres.

All 3 bodies are balls with a small radius compared to the distance of the 3 bodies.

The angle of reflection (phase angle):

$\alpha =$ phase angle of P at B

$$\alpha = 180^\circ - \beta \quad \cos \alpha = \cos(180^\circ - \beta) = -\cos \beta$$

The angle β can be described with the scalar product:

$$\cos \beta = \frac{(\vec{r}_B - \vec{r}_P) \cdot (\vec{r}_S - \vec{r}_P)}{|\vec{r}_P - \vec{r}_B| \cdot |\vec{r}_S - \vec{r}_P|}$$

It follows:

$$\cos \alpha = \frac{(\vec{r}_p - \vec{r}_B) \cdot (\vec{r}_s - \vec{r}_p)}{|\vec{r}_p - \vec{r}_B| \cdot |\vec{r}_s - \vec{r}_p|} \quad (1)$$

Now we explain the following quantities:

R_s = radius of the ball S (fixed star)

R_p = radius of the ball P (planet)

R_B = radius of the ball B (planet with observer)

R_a = radius of the crystalline lens of the observer

The problem is to determine the brightness of the ball P seen from B .

$\Phi_{s,p}$ = luminous flux coming from S through P

I = luminous intensity of S

$\Omega_{s,p}$ = solid angle of P seen from S

With Voigt [6] chapter V.1.1 p.177 we can write approximately the solid angle through:

$$\Omega_{s,p} = \frac{\pi R_p^2}{|\vec{r}_s - \vec{r}_p|^2} \quad R_p \ll |\vec{r}_s - \vec{r}_p|$$

$$\Phi_{s,p} = I \cdot \Omega_{s,p}$$

see Kuchling [3] chapter 27.2.4. p.387.

The luminous flux Φ_α with consideration to the phase, see Montenbruck [4] chapter VI.3.2 p.112:

$$\Phi_\alpha = \frac{1 + \cos(\pi - \alpha)}{2} \cdot \Phi_{s,p} = \frac{1 - \cos \alpha}{2} \cdot \Phi_{s,p} \quad \alpha \text{ in radian measure}$$

We need:

a = albedo of the ball P

For the illumination E that gets the observer on the ball B we obtain with Kuchling [3] chapter 27.2.7. p.389:

$$E = \frac{\Phi_\alpha \cdot a}{|\vec{r}_p - \vec{r}_B|^2}$$

The luminous flux through the observer is, see Kuchling [3] (O 27.21) p.389:

$$\Phi_B = \pi \cdot R_a^2 \cdot E$$

Φ_B and E can be seen as measure of the brightness. If we insert then we obtain:

$$E = \frac{(1 - \cos \alpha) \cdot \Phi_{s,p} \cdot a}{2 \cdot |\vec{r}_p - \vec{r}_B|^2} = \frac{\pi \cdot R_p^2 \cdot I \cdot a \cdot (1 - \cos \alpha)}{2 \cdot |\vec{r}_s - \vec{r}_p|^2 \cdot |\vec{r}_p - \vec{r}_B|^2} \quad (2)$$

These are the formulas of the brightness with the presumption that the whole space is vacuum. In most cases this condition is true in planetary space approximately.

Plane coordinates can be used for $\vec{r}_s, \vec{r}_p, \vec{r}_B$ to the motion in circular orbits on the plane. This can be found at Schröer [5]. We need spherical coordinates for inclined circular orbits.

2 The apparent brightness of exoplanets on inclined orbits

We look at an example with inclined circular orbits. This example is similar to those of sun, earth and Venus. But it is another fixed star HD 10180 (constellation Hydrus) with 2 exoplanets 1 and 3. We mean the inner-most planet and the third planet. This system has got at least 14 planets. The fixed star is far about 130 light-years and has got 1.02 solar masses and 1.1 solar luminous power. HD 10180 is the fixed star S . The exoplanet 3 is presented with the planet B (with observer) and exoplanet 1 is the irradiated planet P . The planets 1 and 3 has got a distance of 0.31 respectively 0.72 astronomical units (AE) from the fixed star. The orbital periods are 61 days respectively 219 days. The masses are 0.1 and 0.04 earth masses. The radii are 0.47 and 0.35 earth's radii. The surface of both planet consists of rock. Both planet have no atmosphere. At both planets the albedo is 0.07. The planets rotate around its axis in 61 days respectively 219 days. The temperatures on planet 1 are from -190 Grad Celsius (C) to +440 Grad C, on planet 3 from -240 Grad C to +230 Grad C.

The orbit radii r_p and r_B , the start angles δ_p and δ_B and the masses m_p and m_B of the planets P and B are known. The fixed star S is in the origin ($\vec{r}_s = \vec{0}$). m_s shall be the mass of the fixed star. Then it is easy to determine the angular velocities of both planets. The angular velocities follow from the equality of gravitation force and centripetal force at circular motion:

$$\frac{G \cdot m_s m_p}{r_p^2} = m_p \cdot r_p \cdot \omega_p^2 \quad \text{it follows:} \quad \omega_p = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot m_s}{r_p^3}}$$

$$\frac{G \cdot m_s m_B}{r_B^2} = m_B \cdot r_B \cdot \omega_B^2 \quad \text{it follows:} \quad \omega_B = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot m_s}{r_B^3}}$$

G is the gravitational constant. The circular orbit of the irradiated planet P shall be inclined relatively to the circular orbit of the observer's planet B . This

inclination angle is denoted with γ and shall be constant. This model will describe the motion of both exoplanets.

The planet B with observer circles in a plane with the orbit vector:

$$\vec{r}_B(t) = r_B \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\delta_B + w_B \cdot t) \\ \sin(\delta_B + w_B \cdot t) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = r_B \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi_B \\ \sin \varphi_B \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Further it is valid $\varphi_p = \delta_p + w_p \cdot t$.

We view the following spherical triangle:

Then the following equations are valid:

$$\sin \varepsilon = \sin \gamma \cdot \sin \varphi_p \quad (3)$$

$$\tan \psi = \cos \gamma \cdot \tan \varphi_p \quad (4)$$

The derivation of both equations is in the appendix. Now we introduce spherical coordinates, see the following figure:

The vector $\vec{r}_p$ can be written as, see Bartsch [1], chapter 7.2.1, p.264,265:

$$\vec{r}_p(t) = r_p \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varepsilon \cdot \cos \psi \\ \cos \varepsilon \cdot \sin \psi \\ \sin \varepsilon \end{pmatrix}$$

The absolute value r_p of $\vec{r}_p$ is given.

From the first chapter we know the formulas:

$$\cos \alpha = \frac{(\vec{r}_p - \vec{r}_B) \cdot (\vec{r}_s - \vec{r}_p)}{|\vec{r}_p - \vec{r}_B| \cdot |\vec{r}_s - \vec{r}_p|}$$

$$E = \frac{\pi \cdot R_p^2 \cdot I \cdot a \cdot (1 - \cos \alpha)}{2 \cdot |\vec{r}_s - \vec{r}_p|^2 \cdot |\vec{r}_p - \vec{r}_B|^2}$$

$$\Phi_B = \pi \cdot R_a^2 \cdot E$$

Here it is $\vec{r}_s = \vec{0}$.

$$\cos \alpha = \frac{(\vec{r}_B - \vec{r}_p) \cdot \vec{r}_p}{|\vec{r}_B - \vec{r}_p| \cdot r_p}$$

$$E = \frac{\pi \cdot R_p^2 \cdot I \cdot a \cdot (1 - \cos \alpha)}{2 \cdot r_p^2 \cdot |\vec{r}_B - \vec{r}_p|^2}$$

Now we must determine the numerator and the denominator of $\cos \alpha$.

We calculate the numerator of $\cos \alpha$:

$$(\vec{r}_B - \vec{r}_p) \cdot \vec{r}_p = \vec{r}_B \cdot \vec{r}_p - r_p^2$$

Because of the scalar product property $r_p^2 = |\vec{r}_p|^2$:

$$\begin{aligned} &= r_B r_p \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi_B \\ \sin \varphi_B \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varepsilon \cos \psi \\ \cos \varepsilon \sin \psi \\ \sin \varepsilon \end{pmatrix} - r_p^2 \\ &= r_B r_p \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi_B \\ \sin \varphi_B \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varepsilon \cos \psi \\ \cos \varepsilon \sin \psi \end{pmatrix} - r_p^2 \\ &= r_p \cdot \left[r_B \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi_B \\ \sin \varphi_B \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varepsilon \cos \psi \\ \cos \varepsilon \sin \psi \end{pmatrix} - r_p \right] \end{aligned}$$

We construct the denominator of $\cos \alpha$:

$$|\vec{r}_B - \vec{r}_p| \cdot r_p = \sqrt{r_B^2 - 2 \cdot \vec{r}_B \cdot \vec{r}_p + r_p^2} \cdot r_p$$

We use the scalar product property $\vec{r}^2 = |\vec{r}|^2$ for $\vec{r} \in \mathbb{R}^3$:

$$\begin{aligned} &= r_p \cdot \left[r_B^2 + r_p^2 - 2r_B r_p \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi_B \\ \sin \varphi_B \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varepsilon \cos \psi \\ \cos \varepsilon \sin \psi \\ \sin \varepsilon \end{pmatrix} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= r_p \cdot \left[r_B^2 + r_p^2 - 2r_B r_p \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi_B \\ \sin \varphi_B \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varepsilon \cos \psi \\ \cos \varepsilon \sin \psi \end{pmatrix} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned}$$

We get:

$$\cos \alpha = \frac{\left(r_B \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi_B \\ \sin \varphi_B \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varepsilon \cos \psi \\ \cos \varepsilon \sin \psi \end{pmatrix} - r_p \right) \cdot r_p}{r_p \cdot \left[r_B^2 + r_p^2 - 2r_B r_p \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi_B \\ \sin \varphi_B \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varepsilon \cos \psi \\ \cos \varepsilon \sin \psi \end{pmatrix} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

In the denominator of the illumination E is the square of the denominator of $\cos \alpha$. We obtain:

$$E = \frac{\pi \cdot R_p^2 \cdot l \cdot a \cdot (1 - \cos \alpha)}{2r_p^2 \cdot \left[r_B^2 + r_p^2 - 2r_B r_p \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varphi_B \\ \sin \varphi_B \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \varepsilon \cos \psi \\ \cos \varepsilon \sin \psi \end{pmatrix} \right]}$$

For the luminous flux:

$$\Phi_B = \pi \cdot R_a^2 \cdot E$$

With M as apparent brightness, E as illumination and Φ_B as luminous flux it is valid (see Voigt [6] chapter IV.1.1. p.139 or Wendker [7] chapter 4.1.2 p.78, equation (4-1)) for the conversion:

$$M_1 - M_2 = -2.5 \cdot \lg \left(\frac{\Phi_{B1}}{\Phi_{B2}} \right) = -2.5 \cdot \lg \left(\frac{E_1}{E_2} \right)$$

Now we calculate the exoplanet's apparent diameter:

$$\sin \frac{\phi}{2} = \frac{R_p}{|\vec{r}_p - \vec{r}_B|}$$

We use the sine law to calculate the angle distance (elongation= ϵ) of planet 1

to fixed star seen from planet 3 .

$$\frac{\sin \beta}{r_B} = \frac{\sin \epsilon}{r_p}$$

With the phase angle ($\alpha = 180^\circ - \beta$) we obtain:

$$\sin \epsilon = \frac{r_p}{r_B} \cdot \sin \alpha$$

We start at point ($t=0$), lower conjunction of planet 1 with the fixed star.

We construct a table with time in days the elongation ϵ in degrees, the apparent diameter ϕ in arc seconds, the distance in km, the apparent brightness in stellar magnitudes and the irradiated part in per cent.

t	ϵ	ϕ	distance Planet 1 and 3	apparent brightness	irradiated part
0	0	9.715072	$64.0 \cdot 10^6$	$+\infty$	0
$\frac{1}{24}$	0.175	9.714964	$64.0007 \cdot 10^6$	+8.78	0.23
$\frac{4}{24}$	0.699	9.713	$64.0114 \cdot 10^6$	+5.76	0.93
$\frac{8}{24}$	1.40	9.708	$64.0456 \cdot 10^6$	+4.25	1.86
$\frac{12}{24}$	2.09	9.700	$64.1025 \cdot 10^6$	+3.36	2.79
$\frac{16}{24}$	2.79	9.688	$64.1821 \cdot 10^6$	+2.74	3.71
$\frac{20}{24}$	3.48	9.672	$64.2842 \cdot 10^6$	+2.26	4.64
1	4.17	9.653	$64.4 \cdot 10^6$	+1.87	5.56
2	8.16	9.476	$65.6 \cdot 10^6$	+0.43	11.02
5	17.8	8.476	$73.4 \cdot 10^6$	-1.16	26.11
7	21.8	7.675	$81.0 \cdot 10^6$	-1.53	34.82
10	24.5	6.587	$94.1 \cdot 10^6$	-1.72	46.06
15	23.0	5.295	$117.4 \cdot 10^6$	-1.72	61.45
20	17.4	4.538	$137.0 \cdot 10^6$	-1.63	74.56
25	9.86	4.136	$150.3 \cdot 10^6$	-1.55	86.57
30	1.43	3.989	$155.9 \cdot 10^6$	-1.52	98.10
35	7.11	4.061	$153.1 \cdot 10^6$	-1.54	90.43
40	15.1	4.371	$142.2 \cdot 10^6$	-1.60	78.63
45	21.5	4.995	$124.5 \cdot 10^6$	-1.69	65.99
50	24.7	6.086	$102.2 \cdot 10^6$	-1.74	51.54
55	21.3	7.809	$79.6 \cdot 10^6$	-1.48	33.42
60	6.84	9.548	$65.1 \cdot 10^6$	+0.80	9.19
65	13.0	9.093	$68.4 \cdot 10^6$	-0.54	18.04
70	23.5	7.163	$86.8 \cdot 10^6$	-1.65	40.08
75	24.1	5.655	$110.0 \cdot 10^6$	-1.74	56.68
80	19.6	4.743	$131.1 \cdot 10^6$	-1.66	70.37
85	12.5	4.238	$146.7 \cdot 10^6$	-1.57	82.65
90	4.28	4.0125	$155.0 \cdot 10^6$	-1.53	94.29
95	4.30	4.0129	$154.9 \cdot 10^6$	-1.53	94.26
100	12.5	4.239	$146.7 \cdot 10^6$	-1.58	82.62

Now we calculate the orbital velocity:

$$v = \frac{2\pi r}{T}$$

r is the distance to fixed star and T the orbital period. Planet 1 and planet 3 have got velocities of 54.562 km per second respectively 36.572 km per second.

3 Appendix

Here we make the derivation of $\sin \epsilon = \sin \gamma \cdot \sin \varphi_p$ and $\tan \psi = \cos \gamma \cdot \tan \varphi_p$ for $0^\circ \leq \varphi_p \leq 360^\circ$.

$\varepsilon =$ latitude angle $-90^\circ \leq \varepsilon \leq 90^\circ$
 $\psi =$ longitude angle

First we view the case $0^\circ \leq \varphi_p \leq 90^\circ$ It is $\varepsilon \geq 0^\circ$.

With Bronstein [2], chapter 2.6.4 3.2 p.209, equation (2.87) and (2.95):

$$\sin \varepsilon = \sin \varphi_p \cdot \sin \gamma$$

$$\cos \gamma = \tan \psi \cdot \cot \varphi_p = \frac{\tan \psi}{\tan \varphi_p} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \tan \psi = \cos \gamma \cdot \tan \varphi_p$$

Now to the case $90^\circ \leq \varphi_p \leq 180^\circ$ with $\varepsilon \geq 0^\circ$:

$$\sin \varepsilon = \sin(180^\circ - \varphi_p) \cdot \sin \gamma = \sin \varphi_p \cdot \sin \gamma$$

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{\tan(180^\circ - \psi)}{\tan(180^\circ - \varphi_p)} = \frac{-\tan \psi}{-\tan \varphi_p} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \tan \psi = \cos \gamma \cdot \tan \varphi_p$$

The case $180^\circ \leq \varphi_p \leq 270^\circ$: $\varepsilon \leq 0^\circ$

$$-\sin \varepsilon = \sin(-\varepsilon) = \sin \gamma \cdot \sin(\varphi_p - 180^\circ) = -\sin \gamma \cdot \sin \varphi_p$$

$$\Rightarrow \sin \varepsilon = \sin \gamma \cdot \sin \varphi_p$$

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{\tan(\psi - 180^\circ)}{\tan(\varphi_p - 180^\circ)} = \frac{\tan \psi}{\tan \varphi_p} \Rightarrow \tan \psi = \cos \gamma \cdot \tan \varphi_p$$

Finally the case $270^\circ \leq \varphi_p \leq 360^\circ$: $\varepsilon \leq 0^\circ$

$$-\sin \varepsilon = \sin(-\varepsilon) = \sin \gamma \cdot \sin(360^\circ - \varphi_p) = -\sin \gamma \cdot \sin \varphi_p$$

$$\Rightarrow \sin \varepsilon = \sin \gamma \cdot \sin \varphi_p$$

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{\tan(360^\circ - \psi)}{\tan(360^\circ - \varphi_p)} = \frac{-\tan \psi}{-\tan \varphi_p} \Rightarrow \tan \psi = \cos \gamma \cdot \tan \varphi_p$$

With that the assertion is proved.

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